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Widening & Outreach Pillar: Task 2 Survey on Researchers Needs and Widening the Perimeter of Data

D11 Dataset from the survey on researchers' needs published

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Executive Summary

In 2021 an online survey was conducted with social sciences researchers using social media data for their research with the purpose to investigate researchers' practices, past experiences, and challenges with social media data. One of the aims was to discover researchers' needs and define practical implications for CESSDA to support in handling social media data.

The dataset and study information can be accessed <https://doi.org/10.7802/2349>.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EFS	Enterprise Feedback Suite
SMD	Social Media Data

Survey on accessing, (re)using, and sharing social media data in academia

In 2021 (July 16th 2021 to October 6th 2021), an online survey (via EFS Survey Unipark - Questback) was conducted with social sciences researchers using social media data for their research.

The purpose of the survey was to

- ... to discover researchers' practices, past experiences, and challenges with the data access to, management of, and sharing of SMD
- ... to discover researchers' needs for data repositories, and to define practical implications for CESSDA to support researchers in data acquisition, management, and archiving of SMD.

Recruitment Plan

The target population of our study consists of social sciences researchers using social media data for their research and having published journal articles based on social media data between 2018 and 2021. They are expected to have collected their own data or to have ownership of the data they reused from others. Excluded were scientists who do not produce any data-related publications and scientists who do not work with social media data. To recruit participants from this target group, the sampling frame is based on e-mail addresses from authors of selected journal papers.

The articles qualified for the study were empirical articles (both qualitative and quantitative) that used social media data. Examples of what the authors of this article considered as relevant social media platforms include the following: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Reddit, Tumblr, Twitch, WhatsApp, Telegram, Signal, TikTok, YouTube and Blogs. Online dating apps, webcam platforms, music apps, and podcasts did not qualify as social media data. Articles excluded from the recruitment process were those that were non-empirical (e.g., methodological or theoretical papers about social media), experimental studies, focused on interviews with (non) users of social media (incl. bloggers and live streamers) or used survey data (e.g., self-reported behavior or preferences towards social media).

The pretest was conducted between June 25th and July 5th, 2021, on a sample of researchers who were not part of the targeted sample. Based on the information that was received from the pretest, an adapted version of the instrument was used for the actual survey. For each article, up to the first five authors (if applicable) were asked to take part in the online survey, in case one of the authors of an article was not reachable (e-mail undeliverable or an absence notice was returned) and to ensure that one or more of the available co-authors

who were responsible for the data access/sharing were contacted. If a notification was received that the author's email address is invalid, new up-to-date email address(es) from institutional or personal webpages (if available) were added to the list. A total of four reminders were sent to respondents between July and August.

Total number of 1738 authors were contacted, 253 participants completed the survey (response rate 19.97%).

Questionnaire

The questionnaire consists of several closed and open-ended questions in seven main sections: a) data acquisition and use of secondary data, b) past data sharing behavior, c) data sharing intentions, d) data documentation, e) use of other forms of data, f) personality and g) demography. The questions to measure factors that influence researchers' data sharing decisions were designed using the Theory of Planned Behavior (Icek Ajzen). In total, the questionnaire had 35 questions, including filter questions.

Data protection measures and access

The generated dataset consists of 344 variables. Several data protection measures were necessary because some of the variables were quasi-identifiers. Quasi-identifiers are variables that can isolate individuals in the dataset, meaning that some variables in the dataset pose a high risk of identification. These are

- variables that could be matched with other information
- variables containing groups with small numbers of respondents
- extreme values

Measures taken to reduce the risk of re-identification of respondents:

- all answers to the open-ended questions were dropped and recodings for the open-ended questions were included
- some of the recoded variables could still be considered as quasi-identifiers and were either dropped or aggregated
- principal investigators will not share the list/names of journals for the recruitment of the participants in any publication or presentation

Some recoded, open-ended questions were not removed from the dataset, when they were identified as non-identifiable information, these were survey responses that were not likely to be recognizable as coming from specific individuals, e.g., opinions and ratings.

Despite these measures, there is still the probability that people could be identified, even if only with a very high effort. Therefore, it was decided to provide the data under "restricted

access”: This means that the research data are not freely available. If users wish to obtain access to the research data with this restriction, they must seek the consent of the data depositor. “SowiDataNet|datorium facilitates this process: At the attempt to download the data, an email form is generated. With this form, access to the data can be requested from the responsible curator. In consultation with the data depositor, the curator will make the data accessible for the user.”¹

The variable report, dataset and questionnaire is stored in SowiDataNet|datorium, a storage and dissemination service of GESIS. The study documentation and data can be accessed via the DOI <https://doi.org/10.7802/2349>.

¹ For further information on the process: <https://data.gesis.org/sharing/#!FurtherInformation>